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Research Article

**EVALUATING THE IMPACT OF PHARMACIST-DRIVEN MENSTRUAL
HYGIENE EDUCATION IN A TERTIARY CARE SETTING IN
TELANGANA****D Sasasvi, Sai Pawan A R, Bogi Joshna, Cheruku Vennela, Mohd Azam Hussain**
Chilkur Balaji College of Pharmacy**Abstract:**

Background: Menstrual hygiene is a vital aspect of women's health, yet inadequate awareness and poor practices contribute to a high incidence of vaginal infections and complications. Pharmacists, as accessible healthcare providers, can play a key role in improving menstrual hygiene awareness.

Methodology: A prospective interventional study was conducted in a tertiary care teaching hospital in Telangana. Participants were divided into two groups: a control group (receiving routine care) and a test group (receiving pharmacist-led menstrual hygiene education). Informed consent was obtained, and data collection was performed using structured KAP (Knowledge, Attitude and Practice) questionnaires. Awareness sessions focused on sanitary product usage, hygiene practices, and infection prevention. The impact was evaluated by comparing pre-and post-education KAP scores.

Results: Many participants had limited menstrual hygiene knowledge before the intervention. The pharmacist-led education significantly improved awareness, leading to better hygiene practices in the test group. A decline in vaginal infections was observed post-intervention. The comparison of pre- and post-education KAP scores showed a substantial improvement in the test group, while the control group exhibited minimal change.

Conclusion: Pharmacist-led education effectively enhanced menstrual hygiene awareness and reduced the risk of vaginal infections among women in a tertiary care hospital. The study underscores the importance of integrating menstrual hygiene education into routine healthcare services to improve women's health outcomes. Larger-scale studies are recommended to validate findings and advocate for pharmacist involvement in menstrual health education.

Keywords: Menstrual hygiene, pharmacist-led education, vaginal infections, KAP model, awareness, tertiary care hospital, intervention, women's health.

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INTRODUCTION:

The menstrual cycle is a natural physiological process involving the shedding of the uterine lining through the vagina, typically lasting 3-7 days and recurring every 21-35 days. ⁽¹⁾ It comprises distinct phases: the follicular, ovulation, and luteal phases, all regulated by hormones such as estrogen, progesterone, FSH and LH. ⁽²⁾ These hormones coordinate the preparation of the endometrium for potential pregnancy and, if fertilisation doesn't occur, trigger menstruation. Menstrual hygiene is crucial, as improper practices can lead to infections such as bacterial vaginosis, candidiasis, or trichomoniasis. Products like reusable cloth, sanitary pads, and reusable pads are used to for menstrual management, each with distinct hygiene protocols and associated risks. ⁽¹⁾

Globally, menstrual hygiene awareness and infrastructure remain inadequate. WHO and UNICEF highlight limited menstrual education and poor sanitation facilities in schools, especially in low-income regions. In Asia, disparities exist between primary and secondary education on menstrual health. In India, over 50% girls are unaware of menstruation before menarche, with cultural taboos and limited access to sanitary products contributing to unsafe practices. ⁽³⁾

Vaginal infections are common during menstruation, often resulting from poor hygiene, hormonal changes, or irritants. Symptoms include abnormal discharge, itching, Odor, and discomfort. Risk factors include antibiotics, tight clothing, and poor hygiene. If untreated, infections can lead to complications such as STI's and chronic inflammation. Preventive measures include proper genital hygiene, avoiding scented products, wearing breathable clothing, and practicing safe sex. Promoting awareness, hygiene education, and access to menstrual products is essential to reduce health risks and improve women's quality of life. ⁽⁴⁾

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

This prospective observational study was conducted over six months in the OPD and IPD of the gynaecology and obstetrics department at Mamatha academy of medical sciences, a 1000-bedded Multispeciality territory care teaching hospital. Female patients aged 11 and above, including pregnant and lactating women diagnosed with vaginal infections or related conditions, were included. Patients unwilling to participate, with psychiatric disorders, or those lost to follow-up were excluded. Data sources included patient case sheets, laboratory reports, and in-person interviews. Structured KAP

(knowledge, Attitude and practice) questionnaires were administered at baseline and monthly for three follow-ups to assess awareness regarding menstrual hygiene and infection risk. The validated KAP tool consisted of 17 questions scoring a total of 68 points. Awareness levels were classified as low (51-68), moderate (34-50), and high 377 using a statistical formula for unlimited populations. Participants were randomly divided into control and test groups using the block randomization technique. The test group received pharmacist-led education sessions on menstrual hygiene, while the control group received routine care. KAP scores and infection severity (daily=3, weekly=2, monthly=1, none=0) were monitored across four stages: baseline, first, second, and final follow-ups. Data were entered into google forms and analysed using SPSS 30.0.0 version. Wilcoxon signed-rank test and spearman's correlation test were used to evaluate the effectiveness of the intervention. The study demonstrated improved awareness and reduced vaginal infection risk through pharmacist-led education on menstrual hygiene practices.

Statistical analysis

Results were analysed using statistical package for the social sciences (SPSS) was the tool used for the statistical analysis of the data. To determine the incidence of the vaginal infections and analysed the pharmacist contribution to lowering the menstrual hygienic complications descriptive statistics were used. The overall KAP scores of the test and control groups are divided by the block randomization technique. For the KAP score, the Wilcoxon signed rank test and the correlation between the various questionnaires were evaluated using spearman's correlation for data analysis purpose used.

RESULTS:

A total of 321 female participants were enrolled, with 161 in the control group and 160 in the test group, mostly aged 22-32 years. The test group had a higher proportion of students (28.12%) and unemployed individuals (39.37%), whereas the control group had more homemakers (75.7%). Most participants had an annual income between ₹1,50,001-₹3,00,000. Married (88.19%) and pregnant women (17.39%) were more common in the control group. A mixed diet was predominant among participants. None reported smoking. Alcohol consumption was noted only in the control group, with 11.80% alcoholics and 13.66% social drinkers, while 97.5% of the test group were non-alcoholic.

TABLE-1 DEMOGRAPHICS DETAILS OF PATIENTS WITH MENSTRUAL HYGIENE AND VAGINAL INFECTIONS

PARAMETERS	CONTROL (n= 161)	TEST (n=160)
Gender	N%	N%
• Female	161(100)	160(100)
Age		
• 11-21	11(6.83)	52(32.5)
• 22-32	67(41.61)	55(34.37)
• 33-43	41(25.46)	39(24.37)
• 44-54	28(17.39)	14(8.75)
• 55-65	14(8.69)	0
Occupational Status		
• Agriculture	50(31.05)	20(12.5)
• Business	40(24.84)	7(4.37)
• Homemaker	26(16.14)	24(15)
• Student	11(6.83)	45(28.12)
• IT	0	12(7.5)
• Nurse	0	12(7.5)
• Teacher	5(3.10)	0
• others	29(18.01)	40(25)
Educational Qualification		
• Primary School	58(36.02)	17(10.62)
• Secondary School	28(17.39)	68(42.5)
• Intermediate	16(9.93)	31(19.37)
• Graduated	20(12.42)	35(21.87)
• Uneducated	39(24.22)	9(5.62)
Employment Status		
• Unemployed	25(15.52)	63(39.37)
• Employed	10(6.21)	24(15)
• Housewife	122(75.7)	73(45.62)
• Retired	4(2.48)	0
Annual income		
• 50000-1,00,000	16(9.93)	4(2.5)
• 1,00,001-1,50,000	41(25.46)	69(43.12)
• 1,50,001-3,00,000	97(60.24)	79(49.37)
• 3,00,001-5,00,000	7(4.34)	8(5.0)
Marital status		
• Married	142(88.19)	97(60.62)
• Unmarried	19(11.80)	63(39.37)
Pregnancy		
• Non pregnant	133(82.60)	146(91.25)
• Pregnant	28(17.39)	14(8.75)
Dietary Preference		
• Veg	18(11.18)	15(9.37)
• Mixed	143(88.81)	145(90.62)
Smoking status		
• Yes	0	0
• No	161(100)	160(100)
Alcohol Status		
• Alcoholic	19(11.80)	0
• Non-alcoholic	120(74.53)	156(97.5)
• Social drinker	22(13.66)	4(2.5)

A total of 321 female patients were enrolled in the study, with 161 in the control group and 160 in the test group. The Majority of participants were aged 22-32 Years. In the test group, there were more students [28.12%]and unemployed individuals [39.37%] compared to the control group, which had a higher percentage of homemakers [75.7%]. Moat participants had an annual income between ₹1,50,001- ₹3,00,000. The Control group had a higher rate of married women

[88.19%] and pregnant individuals [17.39%] compared to the test group. The majority followed a mixed diet, and none reported smoking. Alcohol consumption was observed only in the control group [11.80% alcoholics and 13.66% social drinkers], While 97.5% of the test group were non-alcoholic.

TABLE-2 MEAN AND MEDIAN SCORES OF KAP QUESTIONNAIRE AMONG CONTROL AND TEST GROUP

Descriptive statistics was applied to obtain frequency for various responses.

Mean and Median scores of KAP questionnaires among control and Test group

KAP SCORE	Control-0 Mean ± SD Median (IQR)	Control-1 Mean ± SD Median (IQR)	Control-2 Mean ±SD Median (IQR)	Control-3 Mean ±SD Median (IQR)	Test-0 Mean ±SD Median (IQR)	Test-1 Mean ±SD Median (IQR)	Test-2 Mean ±SD Median (IQR)	Test-3 Mean ±SD Median (IQR)
KAP	43.29±8.196 44(32-54)	43.25±8.258 44(31-54)	43.25±8.818 44(31-54)	42.4±9.25244(29-54)	42.99±7.343 44(33-48)	40.05±6.168 37(36-43)	32.83±4.829 30(36-43)	26.86±4.356 24(25-30)

MEDIAN KAP SCORE FROM BASELINE TO FINAL FOLLOW-UP AMONG CONTROL AND TEST GROUP

Mean KAP score from baseline to final follow-up among control and test group:

KAP scores were estimated for all the enrolled patient’s follow-ups from baseline to final follow-up. At the start [baseline], both groups had low adherence, with KAP scores of [64.70%] among the control and test groups, respectively. By the final follow-up, the control group’s KAP scores remain unchanged while significant improvement was seen in the test group patients, i.e. [35.29].

TABLE-3 MEAN AND MEDIAN OF THE RISK OF VAGINAL INFECTION DURING FOLLOW UPS AMONG CONTROL AND TEST GROUP

Mean and median of the risk of vaginal infection during follow-up among the control and test group

GROUP	Control baseline	Control first follow-up	Control second follow-up	Control final follow-up	Test baseline	Test first follow-up	Test second follow-up	Test final follow-up
Mean ± SD	0.74 ± 0.891	0.74 ± 0.891	0.74 ± 0.891	0.74 ± 0.891	1.49 ± 1.369	1.45 ± 1.36	1.14 ± 1.086	0.73 ± 0.726
Median (IQR)	1 (0.001)	1 (0.001)	1 (0.001)	1 (0.001)	2 (0-3)	2 (0-3)	1 (0-2)	1 (0-1)

Risk of Vaginal Infection During Follow Up Among the Control And Test Group

The risk of vaginal infection in different control and test group follow-ups is shown in the bar graph. The Y-axis shows an average of infection risk values, while the X-axis represents the control and test group at various follow-up points. There is no discernible change in the mean value of 0.74 for the Control group [RVI-CO] to [RVI-C3]. Infection risk in the test group, however, peaks at RVI-T0 [1.49]], then reduces significantly at RVI-T1[1.45] and then further at RVI-T2[1.14].

TABLE-4 COMPARISON OF KAP SCORES BETWEEN THE FOLLOW-UPS AMONG CONTROL AND TEST GROUP

Comparison of KAP scores between the follow-ups among the control and test groups

KAP Scores	Control		Test	
	Z- value	P- value	Z- value	P- value*
T ₀ – T ₁	-2.646	1.000	-9.821	<0.001**
T ₀ – T ₂	-2.646	1.000	-9.105	<0.001**
T ₀ – T ₃	-4.161	1.000	-10.993	<0.001**
T ₁ - T ₂	-2.646	1.000	-8.252	<0.001**
T ₁ – T ₃	-4.161	1.000	-10.987	<0.001**
T ₂ – T ₃	-4.284	1.000	-8.880	<0.001**

*Wilcoxon signed the rank test

**Significant at ≤ 0.05 level

Here, in control group C0 is the baseline, C1 is the first follow-up, C2 is the second follow-up and C3 is the final follow-up while in test group T) is the baseline, T1 is the first follow-up, T2 is the second follow-up and T3 is the final follow-up.

KAP scores were estimated for all the enrolled patients at various follow-ups from baseline to final follow-up. At the start (Baseline), both groups had low adherence, with KAP scores of (64.70%) and (64.70%) among the control and test groups, respectively. By the final follow-up, the control group's KAP scores remain unchanged while significant improvement was seen in the test group patients, i.e. (35.29%)

DISCUSSION:

The world health organization (WHO) reports that vaginal infections, including bacterial vaginosis, candidiasis, and trichomoniasis, are major global reproductive health concerns, affecting millions of women annually. Inadequate menstrual hygiene practices such as using unclean menstrual materials, irregular changing of sanitary products, and poor genital hygiene substantially increase the risk of these infections. Studies have shown that women with limited access to menstrual hygiene products and education are more prone to recurrent infections, which can lead to long-term reproductive health complications. Addressing these issues through enhanced hygiene education, improved access to sanitary products, and healthcare interventions is crucial for reducing infection rates and improving overall women's health and well-being.

The current study found that many women lacked awareness of appropriate menstrual hygiene, resulting in a higher incidence of vaginal infections. Participants commonly reported irregular use of hygiene products, improper disposal methods, and misconceptions about menstrual health. Enhancing knowledge through structured education and public health initiatives is essential for encouraging safe practices and lowering infection risk.

In this study, most participants were aged 22-32 years, and 57.49% reported experiencing at least one vaginal infection in the past year. A related study found 62.3% of women with poor hygiene experienced recurring infections, emphasizing the link between hygiene and infection rates. Adolescents, often without adequate education and access to products, were the most affected group.

In the control group, 36.02% had only primary-level education and displayed limited hygiene awareness. Conversely, 48.12% of the test group had secondary or higher education, reflecting better practices and fewer infections. This underscores the influence of education on menstrual health. Implementing school-based hygiene programs and improving access to affordable products can significantly improve outcomes.

Interestingly, 56.25% of the test group reported symptoms of vaginal infections, compared to 48.44% in the control group, possibly due to better awareness and willingness to report symptoms. Higher rates of frequent and constant infections in the test group

(26.25%) and (16.25%) may also reflect more engagement with healthcare services.

Use of modern hygiene products was higher in the test group (93.12% pads, 2.5% menstrual cups) compared to the control (91.92%, 0%). Baseline IQR scores showed greater improvement in the test group (from 40.05 to 26.86, $P < 0.001^{**}$), confirming the positive impact of pharmacist-led educational interventions.

CONCLUSION:

This prospective observational study assesses menstrual hygiene practices and their impact on the incidence of vaginal infections among 321 female participants of different age groups, primarily aged 22-32 years. The study highlights that 31.05% of participants are engaged in agriculture, 28.12% are students, and many have only primary or secondary education. Additionally, 122 participants are housewives, with an annual income mostly ranging between ₹1,50,000-₹3,00,000. The study found a high prevalence of menstrual irregularities and low usage of feminine hygiene products, with sanitary pads being the most commonly used (93.12%). Participants were divided into a control group (161 patients) that did not receive menstrual hygiene education and a test group (160 patients) that underwent four follow-ups with pharmacist-led awareness sessions using the KAP (Knowledge, Attitude and practice) model. The control group showed no significant improvement, while the test group demonstrated increased awareness, as reflected in KAP scores improving from 42.99 to 26.86, with a significant p-value (< 0.05). Vaginal infections were reported in 171 patients, but the test group showed a reduction in risk from 1.49 to 0.73, compared to a constant 0.74 in the control group. Pharmacist intervention, including educational leaflets, helped reduce infections and highlighted key factors such as improper hygiene and excessive antibiotic use. The study also examined complications like irregular periods, UTIs, and pelvic inflammatory diseases, emphasizing the influence of lifestyle, diet, and sexual activity on reproductive health. Ultimately, the study concludes that pharmacist-led education significantly improves menstrual hygiene awareness, reducing the risk of vaginal infections and promoting better.

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